

Spectrophotometric Studies in the Composition and Stability of Thorium *p*-Nitrobenzeneazochromotropic Acid Chelate

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p-Nitrobenzeneazochromotropic acid (sodium salt) has been found to form a pink-coloured chelate with thorium salts. The chelate has the composition ThK_2 and the λ_{max} lies at 550 $m\mu$, which is stable between pH 3.2 and 7.2. The values of $\log K$ and ΔF° are respectively 10.08 ± 0.15 and -13.92 ± 0.20 kcal. at 25°.

Chelating properties of chromotropic acid are well known. Investigation of uranyl-chromotropic acid chelate by conductometric (Mukherji and Dey, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 113) and spectrophotometric methods (Banerji and Dey, unpublished) has already been made. Formation of coloured chelates of various other metals was described by Mathur and Dey (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1957, 154, 347). Several substituted chromotropic acids have also been tried as chromophoric reagents. Datta (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1956, 149, 270; 153, 89) discussed the analytical applications of some azochromotropic acids. Banerjee used some of these reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of thorium (*Science & Culture*, 1955, 20, 611) and of zirconium (*Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1957, 16, 62). Tolmachev and Lomaskana (*Z. fiz. Khim.*, 1957, 31, 1600) described the interaction of sodium 1,8-dihydroxy-2,2-hydroxyazobenzene-3,6-naphthalene and magnesium ions.

Sommer and Hnilicková (*Chem. Listy*, 1956, 50, 1580) have reviewed the analytical applications of azochromotropic dyes and have mentioned the uses and characteristics of compounds of the following type :

[R=H, $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$, $-\text{COOH}$, $-\text{NO}_2$, $-\text{OH}$, $-\text{OMe}$, $-\text{OEt}$, Me, $-\text{AsO}(\text{OH})_2$ or $-\text{NH}_2$]

The reaction of *p*-nitrobenzeneazochromotropic acid with boric acid was investigated by Komarovski and Polucktov (*Z. Obsch. Chim.*, 1950, 20, 816) and of hydroxybenzeneazochromotropic acid with calcium and magnesium by Kuznecov (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1955, 146, 417). The application of the sulpho compounds in the complexometric determination of thorium and zirconium as metal indicator was studied by Banerjee (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1955, 147, 105; 1956, 149, 270).

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In view of meagre work on metal chelates involving azochromotropic acids, it was thought desirable to investigate the composition and formation of metal chelates with these chelating agents. *p*-Nitrobenzeneazochromotropic acid (sodium salt), known as Chromotrope 2B, forms a pink-coloured complex with thorium salts; the composition and stability of this chelate have been studied by spectrophotometric method in this communication.

The spectrophotometric method, in spite of adverse criticism in recent years, has been found to yield reliable results, particularly with coloured complexes (Woldbye, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1955, 9, 299). For determination of the stability of complexes the method described by Anderson *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1195; 1949, 71, 909, 912), based on the comparison of the compositions of solutions having identical intensity of colour, has been found very convenient. The limitation of the method is that both the interacting solutions must be colorless. The method was subsequently modified by Dey *et al.* (*J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, 6, 314) who were able to apply the method to systems where one of the interactants may be coloured. This method therefore has a much wider application and can be employed conveniently for the study of a large number of chelation reactions.

FIG. 1

Absorption spectra of mixtures of thorium chloride and p-nitrobenzeneazochromotropic acid (sodium salt).

Curve A : reagent $0.5 \times 10^{-4}M$.

Curve B : $c = 0.05 \times 10^{-4}M$ ($\rho = 5$).

Curve C : $c = 0.063 \times 10^{-4}M$ ($\rho = 4$).

Curve D : $c = 0.083 \times 10^{-4}M$ ($\rho = 3$).

Curve E : $c = 0.125 \times 10^{-4}M$ ($\rho = 2$).

Curve F : $c = 0.25 \times 10^{-4}M$ ($\rho = 1$).

EXPERIMENTAL

Aqueous thorium chloride was prepared in CO_2 -free, double distilled water, using BDH AnalaR salt, and was estimated gravimetrically as ThO_2 . Solutions were freshly prepared to avoid effects due to hydrolysis. B.D.H. reagent grade Chromotrope 2B (abbreviated in this paper as CTB) was used for preparing aqueous solutions.

Spectrophotometric measurements were made exactly as described by Banerji and Dey (this *Journal*, 1961, 38, 121).

Nature of the Complexes Formed.—The method of Vosburgh and Cooper (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437) was employed to determine the nature of complexes formed in aqueous solution. Mixtures containing different proportions of thorium : Chromotrope 2B (1:0, 1:1, 1:2, etc.) were prepared and the absorbance was determined at different wave lengths. The results are plotted graphically in Fig. 1, where it may be seen that the λ_{max} of the reagent lies at $520 \text{ m}\mu$ (curve A). In curves D, E, and F λ_{max} lies at $550 \text{ m}\mu$, which is the region of maximum absorption of the chelate. In curves B and C, where the proportion of the chelating agent is large, the observed maximum absorption is at $540 \text{ m}\mu$, instead of $550 \text{ m}\mu$, which may be due to the excess of the free dye present in the systems.

FIG. 2

Equimolecular solutions at $550 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\rho=1$).Curve A : $c = 1.00 \times 10^{-4} M$.Curve B : $c = 0.67 \times 10^{-4} M$.

FIG. 3

Equimolecular solutions at $580 \text{ m}\mu$.Curve C : $c = 0.56 \times 10^{-4} M$.Curve D : $c = 0.50 \times 10^{-4} M$.← $[\text{Th}^{4+}]/([\text{Th}^{4+}] + [\text{CTB}])$ →

FIG. 4

Non-equimol. soln. at 550 m μ .Curve A: $c = 1.00 \times 10^{-4}M$ ($p = 0.66$).Curve B: $c = 0.67 \times 10^{-4}M$ ($p = 1.50$).

FIG. 5

Non-equimol. soln. at 580 m μ .Curve C: $c = 0.50 \times 10^{-4}M$ ($p = 2.0$).Curve D: $c = 0.40 \times 10^{-4}M$ ($p = 2.0$).← Volume of ThCl₄ in c.c. →

Stoichiometry of the Components.—Job's method of continued variation (*Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 928; *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113; 1936, xi, 6, 97) was employed for determining the composition of the complex. The total volume of the mixture was kept at 50 c.c. in each case. Absorbance measurements were done at 550 m μ and 580 m μ . Several experiments were performed with equimolecular and non-equimolecular solutions to obtain conclusive evidence of the composition. Some of the typical observations are plotted in Figs. 2—5, where the difference in absorbance by the mixture and that by the chelating agent alone, assuming that no chelation occurs, is plotted against the composition of the mixture. The pH, of the mixtures was kept constant in one set of experiments and in the various sets the pH was between 3.3 and 5.4 (colour of the chelating agent was not affected by this change in pH).

In the legends to the figures, c represents the concentration of thorium ions, c' that of Chromotrope 2B, i.e., $p = c'/c$.

Influence of pH on the Stability of the Chelate.—The absorbance of mixtures of $0.25 \times 10^{-4}M$ thorium chloride and $0.50 \times 10^{-4}M$ Chromotrope 2B at different pH's were measured at various wave lengths. The results are plotted in Fig. 6 where λ_{\max} lies at 550 m μ , between pH 3.2 and 5.9 of the mixture. This shows that the chelate is stable in this range of pH.

FIG. 6
Influence of pH on absorbance.

DISCUSSION

From the data plotted in Figs. 2—5, we may get information about the composition of the complex, as shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Fig. No.	Curve No.	$c \times 10^4$.	ρ .	Wave length.	Peak occurring at vol. of ThCl_4 .	Composition of the chelate (Th : CTB).
2	A	1.00M	1.0	550 $m\mu$	16.7c.c.	1 : 2
	B	0.67	1.0	550	16.7	1 : 2
	C	0.56	1.0	550	16.7	1 : 2
	D	0.50	1.0	550	16.7	1 : 2
3	A	1.00	1.0	580	16.7	1 : 2
	B	0.67	1.0	580	16.7	1 : 2
	C	0.56	1.0	580	16.7	1 : 2
	D	0.50	1.0	580	16.7	1 : 2
4	A	1.00	0.66	550	12.5	1 : 2
	B	0.67	1.50	550	21.4	1 : 2
	C	0.50	2.00	550	25.0	1 : 2
	D	0.40	2.00	550	25.0	1 : 2
5	A	1.00	0.66	580	12.5	1 : 2
	B	0.67	1.50	580	21.4	1 : 2
	C	0.50	2.00	580	25.0	1 : 2
	D	0.40	2.00	580	25.0	1 : 2

The composition of the chelate investigated therefore corresponds to $\text{Th}(\text{CTB})_2$. It may also be seen that the composition is revealed in the case of non-equimolecular solutions also. Thus it is not possible to calculate the stability by Job's method.

The apparent formation constant has been calculated from absorbance data, as shown in Fig. 7. The absorbance of the various mixtures was measured at $550 \text{ m}\mu$, keeping the total volume of the solutions at 50 c.c. The observed absorbance (not the difference as in Figs. 2—5) was plotted against composition of the mixture. Thorium ions are colorless and hence the colour of the mixtures is due to the chelating agent and the coloured chelate. With the progressive increase in the concentration of the thorium ions added and with the formation of the chelate, the amount of the free chelating agent decreases. Thus, in the descending portions of the curves, where the metal ions are in excess, it may be reasonable to assume that a majority of the reagent is bound up in the complex, which is fairly stable, and does not contribute appreciably to the colour of the mixture. The colour of the solution, *i.e.*, the absorbance in these regions of the curve, is therefore principally due to the coloured chelate alone.

FIG. 7
Formation constant from absorption spectra at $550 \text{ m}\mu$.

Fig. 7 represents such a graph, where four concentrations of the reactants ($\rho=1$) are represented by curves A to D. An arbitrary value for absorbance (say 0.25) was chosen and the concentrations of the reactants were read from the graph, in the descending portions of the curves. It may be reasonable to assume that the amounts of complexes formed from these quantities

of the reactants are identical since they have the same absorbance values. Hence in the equilibrium :

if x represents the concentration of the chelate at equilibrium, and a and b , the concentrations initially present of the metal ion and the chelating agent, respectively, the formation constant is given by :

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-2x)^2} \quad \dots (i)$$

Taking two values of a and b , showing the same absorbance, i.e., the same value of x , we have

$$K = \frac{x}{(a_1-x)(b_1-2x)^2} = \frac{x}{(a_2-x)(b_2-2x)^2} \quad \dots (ii)$$

$$\text{or } 4x^2 [(a_1 + b_1) - (a_2 + b_2)] + x [(b_2^2 - b_1^2) + 4(a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1)] + (a_1 b_1^2 + a_2 b_2^2) = 0$$

$$\therefore x = \frac{-[(b_2^2 - b_1^2) + 4(a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1)] \pm \sqrt{[(b_2^2 - b_1^2) + 4(a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1)]^2 - 16(a_1 + b_1)(a_2 + b_2)(a_1 b_1^2 + a_2 b_2^2)}}{8[(a_1 + b_1) - (a_2 + b_2)]} \quad \dots (iii)$$

Thus, from equation (iii), we can calculate the value of x and therefrom the value of K by substitution in equation (i).

The free energy of formation can be obtained from the relation :

$$\Delta F^\circ = -RT \ln K$$

where ΔF° is the free energy of formation, R , the gas constant, and T , the absolute temperature.

In the system thorium - *p*-nitrobenzeneazochromotropic acid, the value of $\log K$ and of ΔF° work out respectively to be 10.08 ± 0.15 and -13.92 ± 0.20 kcal. at 25° .

p-Nitrobenzeneazochromotropic acid may be represented by structure (I : $R = \text{NO}_2$).

From the absorption spectra studies of the reagent (sodium salt) in different media Sommer *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) obtained the following values for λ_{max} .

TABLE II

Medium.	λ_{max} (m μ)
Aqueous solution	517
0.1N - H ₂ SO ₄	517
0.1N - NaOH	537 (430)
H ₂ SO ₄ (conc.)	582 (413)

There are then three ionisable forms (for the sodium salt), which may be represented by :

(In acidic medium).

[In neutral or feebly acidic medium].

(In alkaline medium).

In the case of the chelate investigated here, the medium was on the acidic side, showing preponderance of the structure represented by (II). It might therefore be suggested that the thorium chelate will have a structure as shown below :

[Th-CTB chelate]